

Standard Operating Procedure	Version: 2
Household Participant Stool Sample Collection	
Effective date: 01/07/19	Next Review Due:

Author	Signed	Date
Dr Derek Cocker		01/07/19

Reviewer	Signed	Date
Dr Nicholas Feasey		01/07/19
Authoriser	Signed	Date
Dr Nicholas Feasey		01/07/19

Version History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	01/04/19	Initial version
2.0	01/07/19	Changes made after pilot phase

1. Introduction

This method is applicable to the collection of human stool samples from household participants included in the DRUM study.

The proportion of patients admitted to hospitals in Uganda and Malawi with invasive infections caused by ESBL resistant Enterobacteriaceae including ESBL E coli (ESBL-E) and ESBL K pneumoniae (ESBL-K) is increasing. Given the reduced availability of Carbapenems, many of these drug-resistant infections are locally untreatable. To understand the drivers of this antimicrobial resistance, further evidence of the role of household environment contamination on human and animal carriage with ESBL-E and ESBL-K is required.

2. Purpose

This method describes the process of collecting stool samples from human household participants that will subsequently be screened for the presence of ESBL *E. coli* / *K. pneumoniae* as part of the DRUM study.

3. Responsibilities

- Field workers
 - Consent for the collection of human stool
 - Inform participants on how to collect and store stool, according to this SOP
 - Collection of human stool via rectal swabs, according to this SOP
 - Correct labelling of collection samples
 - Prompt transport of collected samples to the laboratory
 - Completion of sample collection log
- Study Laboratory Technicians
 - Receive samples from field and complete sample collection log
 - Register samples on DRUM teleform LIMS system.
 - Inform Study Laboratory Technicians of sample arrival
 - Ensure prompt collection of study samples from laboratory reception

- Double-check correct sample labelling as in this SOP
- Principal Investigators
 - Ensure field worker training in sample collection processes is provided
 - Undertake quality control checks of sample collection and processing.

4. Procedure

4.1. Materials and Equipment

Gloves

Blue topped sterile stool collection pots (with spoon inside) – 1 per participant

Blue transwabs (rectal swabs) – 2 per participant

Medical pulp bowls

Sterile collection bags

Hand disinfectant

4.2. Human Stool Collection (Sterile Pot)

Inform each household participant of how to use the medical pulp bowl and collection pot for obtaining stool. Stool collection should be done by each individual wherever possible to reduce cross contamination.

- 1) Introduce yourself and gain verbal consent for sample collection
- 2) If the participant is not confused and is willing to collect the stool sample themselves, give them the equipment needed (blue topped universal pot / medical pulp bowl / plastic sample bag) and tell them, you will return the next day to collect the sample.
- 3) Please show them how to use the spoon attached to the lid of the universal container and medical pulp bowl to aid collection. Inform the participants that the bowls are biodegradable and can be disposed of in a pit latrine or returned to the study team for incineration.
- 4) Once stool is placed in the collection pot, screw the lid on tightly and place each sample pot in an individual sealable plastic bag whilst waiting for collection.

- 5) Sample pots should be clearly labelled by the field team to ensure that each container is allocated to an individual participant. Please reiterate the importance of this allocation when giving each household member the collection equipment. Please use the colour scheme to ensure participants are able to identify the stool that belonged to them. Assign them a colour and include a colour card in the sample collection bag.
- 6) Remind the participants that the aim is to collect as large a sample as possible, with a minimum of 2mls (although if only a smaller sample can be obtained this should be sent).
- 7) Nappy liners and nappies can be given to help facilitate capturing of samples from children. Sample collection does not need to be sterile, and samples can be scraped from chitenges or nappies via the blue spoon into the container if needed. If in your judgement this is not possible then perform a rectal swab instead (**see 4.3**).
- 8) If in your judgment the participant is incontinent of faeces and will not be able to provide a stool sample themselves, or desires rectal swab sampling in preference to collection of stool via a pot, then perform a rectal swab instead (**see 4.3**).
- 9) Inform the participants to ideally store the sample in a cool location, away from light, until collection the following day.
- 10) The field team will collect the samples the following day. Once sample pots have been filled, ensure that the lids are screwed on tightly; labelled appropriately, placed into a sealed plastic bag and when ready for transport put all household samples into a container for transport to the laboratory (**see 4.4**).
- 11) Before leaving, ensure that areas where samples have been stored overnight are cleaned down appropriately (see local health and safety methods), so as to not pose a risk to human health.

4.3. Human Stool Collection (Rectal swab)

Rectal swabs should be collected only for participants who are unable, in your judgement, to provide a stool sample.

- 1) Introduce yourself and gain verbal consent for sample collection
- 2) Don gloves
- 3) Open swab
- 4) Ask patient to roll onto their side, pull knees up to stomach to expose anus
- 5) Insert swab into anus 2-3cm
- 6) Gently rotate swab
- 7) Remove and put swab into container
- 8) *Repeat with a second swab*
- 9) Label swabs and place into a container for transport to the laboratory (**see 4.4**)

4.4 Sample Storage and Transport

Protect all samples from direct sunlight and transport in an insulated container or refrigerator at 2 – 8°C. Samples should be analysed as soon as is practicable and storage under the above conditions should not exceed 24 h before the commencement of analysis.

5. Health and Safety

Please refer to risk assessment tools and local health and safety guidelines

7. Training Log

The following have been trained in this SOP and have adequate knowledge of its contents

Name of Trainer	Name of Trainee	Signature/Date of Trainer	Signature/Date of Trainee